

Task 4.4A (Subtask 2): Develop Methods to Evaluate and Report on Metadata Quality

Technical Report

Owner: Stanford University

Revision History

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Purpose

This report outlines the methods and criteria designed to evaluate and report metadata quality in the RADx Data Hub. Through a combination of automated tools and manual reviews, the report identifies areas for improvement. This work corresponds to subtask 2 (*Develop methods to evaluate and report on metadata quality*) of task 4.4A (*Evaluate and Improve Metadata Quality and Reusability*).

Contents

Introduction.....	3
Scope of the Evaluation.....	3
Metadata Level.....	4
Study Metadata Instances.....	4
Data File Metadata Instances.....	5
Schema Level.....	8
Template Fields.....	8
Template Value Sets.....	8
Metadata Evaluation Criteria.....	9
Metadata Evaluation Methods.....	17
Automated Evaluation.....	17
Manual Review.....	18
Evaluation Reports.....	19
Metadata Evaluation Database.....	19
Metadata Instances Summary.....	22
Templates Summary.....	25
Evaluation Results.....	26
Ongoing Evaluation.....	29
Resources.....	29
Glossary.....	30

Introduction

Task 4.4A (Subtask 2), also referred to as 4.4A(2), focuses on developing methods to evaluate and report the quality of RADx Data Hub metadata. This report outlines a semi-automated metadata evaluation approach built on three key components:

- A list of **Metadata Evaluation Criteria**.
- A software tool for automated metadata evaluation, known as the **RADx Metadata Evaluator**.
- A **Framework for Documenting and Reporting** metadata evaluation issues.

The subsequent sections detail the scope of the evaluation, the criteria employed, the functionality of the Metadata Evaluator tool, and the manual process for reviewing and refining its findings.

As of January 30, 2025, our preliminary evaluation evaluated 181 study metadata instances and 218 data file metadata instances, along with their respective templates. In total, 586 issues were identified, with an additional 58 issues pending further confirmation. These issues will be investigated in the coming months through a collaborative effort with the Booz Allen Hamilton team. Subsequently, the updated metadata will be re-evaluated, and any remaining issues will be re-investigated in an iterative process.

Scope of the Evaluation

This work evaluates the quality of metadata for the two primary RADx Data Hub entities—studies and data files—at two levels: the metadata level (individual metadata instances) and the schema level (metadata templates). Figure 1 outlines the structure of the metadata.

Figure 1. Structure of metadata in the RADx Data Hub evaluated in 4.4A-2 task.

Metadata Level

Metadata instances are CEDAR artifacts that capture metadata created based on the predefined templates. The RADx Data Hub stores metadata for two entity types: studies and data files.

Study Metadata Instances

A concrete study metadata record is a study metadata instance. In this task, we evaluated the study metadata for 181 studies, which corresponds to 181 study metadata instances. The evaluation of study metadata instances focuses on the values displayed in the Study Information section of the Study Overview page. These values encompass the common key fields about the study, such as Study Description, Study Domain, Keywords and relevant fields (Figure 2).

While studies may include additional metadata beyond what is displayed, the evaluation focuses exclusively on publicly available metadata.

Data File Metadata Instances

In the RADx Data Hub, data files in CSV format are accompanied by a corresponding metadata file in CEDAR's JSON-LD format, containing structured descriptions of the data file's attributes and contents. This metadata file contains a single data file metadata instance, representing the detailed metadata for a data file.

Data file metadata files are provided and submitted by study PIs or (C)DCCs. Submitters can include metadata files alongside supporting documents (e.g., study documentation and README files), data files, and data dictionary files. Once uploaded, the metadata files undergo basic validation to ensure that their JSON schema aligns with the Data File Metadata Template, all required fields are present, and the values conform to specified constraints (e.g., data type, cardinality).

These metadata files can be downloaded in JSON or YAML format or viewed directly on the RADx Data Hub by clicking the *Visualize Metadata File* icon in the Metadata column. The displayed metadata file is shown in Figure 3. All publicly accessible data file metadata files undergo evaluation.

Adapting Community-Based Task-Shifting for the COVID-19 Response Among Underserved Populations in Piedmont, North Carolina (ACT UP) (4.41 MB)

[Home](#) › [Study Explorer](#) › [Study Overview](#)

Study Information

dbGaP Study Accession: [phs002581](#)

NIH Institute/Center: NIAID

RADx Data Program: RADx-UP

Release Date: 04/11/2024

DOI: 10.60773/c65t-e596

Study Description: In North Carolina and nationally, Black and Hispanic/Latinx communities have been disproportionately affected by COVID-19 due to multi-level risk factors and barriers to testing, prevention, and care, but have not benefited from a clinical and public health response commensurate with the magnitude of the problem. To address this, a proven implementation strategy from the global HIV response community-based task shifting was adapted to reach underserved and vulnerable Black and Hispanic/Latinx communities with COVID-19 testing and linkage to care, vaccination, and other preventative measures in rural central North Carolina, and to evaluate the effects of this strategy on important health service and implementation outcomes. This project improved testing access for underserved communities being missed by current testing approaches, and generated new insights into a promising implementation strategy that could be leveraged to enhance ongoing pandemic response efforts and delivery of COVID-19 vaccines and other prevention interventions.

Updated Date: 04/17/2024

Principal Investigator: Herce, Michael

Has Data Files: Yes

Study Domain: Community Outreach Programs; Testing Rate or Uptake; Vaccination Rate or Uptake; Virological Testing

Data Collection Method: Interview or Focus Group; Survey

Keywords: Testing Disparities

Study Design: Longitudinal Cohort

Multi-Center Study: No

Data Types: Behavioral; Electronic Medical Records; Questionnaire or Survey; Social

Study Start Date: 11/01/2020

Study End Date: 10/31/2022

Species: Human Data

Estimated Cohort Size: 1050

Study Population Focus: Adults; African Americans; Essential Workers; Hispanics or Latinos; Immigrants; Older Adults or Elderly; Racial or Ethnic Minorities; Rural Communities; Underserved or Vulnerable Populations

Figure 2. Partial Study Metadata for phs002581 in the RADx Data Hub.

Data File Titles [?] ^

Title * [?]

Language [?]

Data File Identity [?] ^

File Name [?]

Version [?]

SHA256 digest [?]

Data File Language [?] ^

Primary Language [?]

Data File Subjects [?] ^

Subject Identifier [?]

http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/MESH/D000086382)"/>

Data File Descriptions [?] ^

Description Language [?]

Figure 3. Example of data file metadata as displayed in the RADx Data Hub.

Schema Level

Evaluation at the schema level focuses on the metadata template. A metadata template is a predefined structure or model that serves as a blueprint for standardizing and organizing metadata.

[The data file metadata template](#) was designed by the Stanford team and has already been implemented on the RADx Data Hub. Currently, all available data file metadata files on the hub are generated based on this template. However, a study metadata template was previously unavailable. To address this gap and facilitate the evaluation of study metadata, a dedicated study metadata template has been developed as part of this work. This new study metadata template builds on the study metadata already present on the RADx Data Hub.

Both templates reference CEDAR templates for metadata storage. CEDAR templates have two key components: template fields and value sets. These components are described below.

Template Fields

Template fields represent standardized data elements or placeholders within a template, specifying how information should be structured. The study metadata template is being developed using the same field names as those in the RADx Data Hub, meaning that the template field evaluation directly assesses the corresponding fields in the RADx Data Hub.

For instance, as shown in Figure 2, study metadata template fields include **dbGaP Study Accession**, **NIH Institute/Center**, **RADx Data Program**, **Release Date**, and others. Similarly in Figure 3, data file metadata template fields include **Title**, **Language**, **File Name**, **Version**, **SHA256 digest**, **Primary Language**, **Subject Identifier** and **Description Language**.

Template Value Sets

Template value sets are predefined lists or collections of permissible values for specific template fields. In the data file metadata template, some fields draw their

values from various ontologies. Similarly, in the RADx Data Hub, specific study fields, such as Study Population Focus, utilize value sets that are incorporated into the facets for filtering studies on the Study Explorer page, as illustrated in Figure 4. Therefore, the evaluation includes value sets for both study and data file metadata.

Figure 4. A screenshot of the RADx Data Hub website displaying a value set with permissible values for Study Population Focus.

Metadata Evaluation Criteria

Metadata evaluation criteria serve as foundational reference for assessing the quality, consistency, and usability of metadata. The evaluation approach presented in this document includes both manual reviews, conducted by two expert reviewers, and automated evaluations, ensuring a thorough examination from multiple perspectives. While these criteria provide a unified standard for evaluating metadata, different entities, such as metadata instances, template fields and template value sets, require tailored criteria based on their unique characteristics. By applying entity-specific criteria within a consistent overall framework, we ensure that every aspect of the evaluation is performed according to a consistent, unified standard. The following tables present the metadata evaluation criteria used as a

reference to evaluate RADx Data Hub metadata. Table 1 lists the criteria used to evaluate metadata instances. Tables 2 and 3 contain the criteria used to evaluate template fields and value sets.

Table 1. Metadata evaluation criteria for metadata instances.

Criterion ID	Criterion	Description	Notes / Examples
M-COMP	Overall Completeness	Percentage of fields with a non-empty value	Calculated for both Study Metadata and Data File Metadata. For instance, a metadata template with a total of 10 fields, where 3 fields have empty values, would have an overall completeness value of 70%.
M-COMP-REQ	Completeness of Required Fields	Percentage of required fields with a non-empty value	The calculation is similar to Overall Completeness but applies exclusively to required fields.
M-COMP-REC	Completeness of Recommended Fields	Percentage of recommended fields with a non-empty value	The calculation is similar to Overall Completeness but applies exclusively to recommended fields.
M-COMP-OP	Completeness of Optional Fields	Percentage of optional fields with a non-empty value	The calculation is similar to Overall Completeness but applies exclusively to optional fields.
M-CONS	Consistency	Comparison of metadata across a collection to confirm that values expected to have the same content are identical	<p>Study Metadata Consistency (internal consistency within study metadata fields)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study Description: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Check it aligns with related metadata fields. For example: If the study description includes participants information, it should correspond accurately to the <i>Estimated Cohort Size</i> • Fields related to each other should be consistent. Key evaluated fields are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Estimated Cohort Size vs. Cohort Size Range ○ Acknowledgement Statement vs. NIH Grant or Contract Number(s), NIH Institute/Center, RADx Data Program, dbGaP Study Accession, and RAPIDS Link ○ Funding Opportunity Announcement (FOA) Number vs. FOA URL ○ Has Data Files vs. whether or not there are actually data files present • Study metadata on the Study Explorer page and

			<p>the Study Overview page should be consistent.</p> <p>Data File Consistency (internal consistency within data file metadata fields):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure that the given name and family name fields are consistent with the full name field to maintain accurate representation. Related fields are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Creator/Contributor Full Name ○ Creator/Contributor Given Name ○ Creator/Contributor Family Name <p>Cross-Check Between Study Metadata and Data File Metadata:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fields common to both study metadata and data file metadata should be identical. Key evaluated fields in the Data File Metadata are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PHS Identifier ○ Study Name <p><i>Note: We are aware of the discrepancies between the Estimated Cohort Size in the study metadata and the participant records in the data file metadata. Booz Allen informed us that the Estimated Cohort Size may not precisely match the actual number of participants. Additionally, the participant count in the metadata file does not necessarily reflect the final study enrollment, as data uploads often come from studies that are still enrolling. Booz Allen plans to replace estimated numbers with actual counts as studies conclude.</i></p>
M-ACCU	Accuracy	Correctness of metadata values in accurately representing the actual data	<p>Study Metadata Accuracy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-checked against metadata available in the NIH RePORTER using the provided <i>NIH Grant or Contract Number(s)</i> to ensure correctness and alignment. Key evaluated fields are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ NIH Institute/Center ○ Funding Opportunity Announcement (FOA) Number • Verified to confirm that the URL resolves to the corresponding study, ensuring accurate linkage and proper study representation. Key evaluated field is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ClinicalTrials.gov URLs
M-VAL	Validity	Conformance of metadata to	Study Metadata Validity:

		predefined schemas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verify that all required metadata fields are populated. • Ensure that all field values meet defined constraints, including but not limited to data types and cardinality. <p>Data File Metadata Validity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate that the provided file is a valid JSON file. • Validate the JSON schema against the Data File Metadata Template • Ensure that all values conform to constraints defined in the template.
M-ACCE	Accessibility	Presence and resolvability of provided URLs	<p>Study Metadata Accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the accessibility of all link-type fields, including the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Study Website URL ○ ClinicalTrials.gov URL ○ Publication URLs ○ Funding Opportunity Announcement (FOA) URL ○ RAPIDS Link
M-CVC	Controlled Vocabulary Consistency	Consistency in the use of controlled vocabularies	<p>Study Metadata Controlled Vocabulary Consistency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the value of certain fields in the code list values. Key evaluated fields are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Study Population Focus ○ Cohort Size Range ○ Study Domain ○ Study Design ○ Data Collection Method ○ NIH Institute / Center ○ RADx Data Program <p>Data File Metadata Controlled Vocabulary Consistency:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate the value of controlled term fields that are consistent with the predefined ontologies. Key evaluated fields are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data File Identity/Identifier Type ○ Data File Subjects/Subject Identifier ○ Data File Creators/Creator Type ○ Data File Creators/Creator Identifier Scheme ○ Data File Creators/Creator Affiliation Identifier Scheme ○ Data File Creators/Creator Role ○ Data File Related Resources/Related Resource Identifier Type

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data File Related Resources/Related Resource Type Category ○ Data File Contributors/Contributor Type ○ Data File Contributors/Contributor Identifier Scheme ○ Data File Contributors/Contributor Affiliation Identifier Scheme ○ Data File Contributors/Contributor Role ○ Data File Rights/License Name ○ Data File Dates/Event Type ○ Data File Parent Studies/ Study Identifier Scheme ○ Data File Funding Sources/Funder Identifier Scheme
M-UNIQ	Uniqueness	Distinctness of metadata instances without duplication across the system	<p>Study Metadata Uniqueness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Evaluate all study PHS numbers are distinct. <p>Data File Metadata Uniqueness:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Check the uniqueness of data file metadata, with a particular focus on distinguishing metadata between origcopy and transformcopy.
M-LIN	Linguistic Quality	Grammatical and lexical accuracy of metadata values	<p>Study Metadata Linguistic Quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extra Spaces: Identify any unnecessary spaces for consistency. ● Grammar correctness: Ensure that all text adheres to proper grammatical rules for clarity and professionalism. ● Spelling Correctness: Ensure that there are no spelling errors. ● Punctuations: Identify any missing punctuation. <p>Data File Metadata Linguistic Quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Extra Spaces: Identify any unnecessary spaces for consistency.
M-STRUCT	Structural Quality	Clarity, organization, and logical structure of study description text in alignment with predefined	This applies exclusively to study descriptions. Currently, all study descriptions in the RADx Data Hub lack a clear structure, making it challenging for users to locate and find specific information efficiently.

		templates or guidelines	
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Table 2. Metadata evaluation criteria for template fields.

Criterion ID	Criterion	Description	Notes / Examples
TF-COMP	Completeness	Schema includes all necessary fields to describe the data comprehensively	Data File Metadata Template: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Metadata related to CSV data file properties and sample properties are not captured in the existing template.
TF-ACCU	Accuracy	Field names accurately represent the intended information	It applies to both Study Metadata Template and Data File Metadata Template. <i>Note: In some cases, even if terms are not entirely accurate, we may choose to retain their original names. For example, the Data Type field describes the domain to which the data pertains, which is an unconventional use of the term "Data Type." However, since this terminology originates from the dbGaP MTA form, we may decide to keep it unchanged.</i>
TF-REL	Relevance	Fields are directly relevant to the intended purpose and audience of the metadata, with no unnecessary or redundant fields	Data File Metadata Template: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The field will be considered unnecessary if no instances contain a value for it.
TF-ACCE	Accessibility	Template is accessible through documentation or online repositories in machine-readable formats (e.g., JSON)	Data File Metadata Template: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Verify whether the template is available and accessible in CEDAR. Confirm that the template documentation is accessible online. Ensure that the template is available in JSON format.
TF-STRUCT	Structural Quality	Template's structural definitions align with the actual	Data File Template: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure the template structure is appropriate. Confirm that the defined cardinality aligns with actual requirements.

		requirements or intended usage	
TF-LING	Linguistic Quality	Field names are both grammatically and lexically accurate	<p>This applies to both the Study Metadata Template and the Data File Metadata Template.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plural Check: When multiple values are allowed for a field, its name should reflect this flexibility. For example, since multiple values are permitted for the Data Collection Method field, it should be renamed to Data Collection Methods.
TF-DOC	Documentation	Clear and comprehensive documentation for each field, explaining its purpose, expected data type, and any applicable constraints	<p>Data File Metadata Template:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Confirm that clear and comprehensive documentation and instructions for the template is provided.
TF-STAND	Standardization	Consistent naming conventions, such as camelCase, snake_case, or Title Case, across all field names and templates	<p>This applies to both the Study Metadata Template and the Data File Metadata Template.</p> <p>For instance, field names in the Data File Metadata Template are written in title case, except for “SHA256 digest”.</p>

Table 3. Metadata evaluation criteria for template value sets.

Criterion ID	Criterion	Description	Notes / Examples
TVS-ACCE	Accessibility	Value sets are all accessible through BioPortal	<p>Data File Metadata Template:</p> <p>The original IRIs within Ontology for Generic Dataset Metadata Template (FDC-GDMT) vocabulary are no longer resolvable due to the permanent unavailability of the server hosting the IRI descriptions. To address this issue, the vocabulary has been replaced with an equivalent under a new, controlled prefix. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A new W3Id prefix has been created to ensure consistent and reliable resolution of terms.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The prefix for GDMT IRIs has been updated from https://fairdatacollective.org/ to https://w3id.org/gdmt/ <p>The replacement ontology is Generic Dataset Metadata Template Vocabulary (GDMT).</p>
TVS-COMP	Completeness	Value sets include all necessary values to provide a comprehensive coverage of the data domain	<p>Data File Metadata Template: Certain fields in the current Data File Metadata Template are designed to utilize the FDC-GDMT ontology. For instance, the value of the Contributor Role field is expected to align with the values specified under the Contributor Type branch of the GDMT ontology.</p> <p>RADx-rad requires the ability to differentiate between various types of Principal Investigator (PI) roles. Specifically, there are center PIs overseeing multiple subprojects and PIs assigned to these individual subprojects. The generic role classifications in RADx metadata, which are based on DataCite standards, do not appear to fully accommodate these distinctions at first glance.</p>
TVS-ACCU	Accuracy	Value sets are precise, correctly represent the intended concepts, and align with domain standards	<p>Study Metadata Template: The meanings of some strings in the study metadata code list are ambiguous. An example is the use of "Time-Series" in the Study Design field, which is misleading. A "time series" typically refers to a collection of data arranged in chronological order. The correct term should be "<i>Interrupted Time Series</i>". However, even this term describes a specific "<i>interventional study design</i>" (another value in the set). As a result, studies tagged with "<i>Time Series</i>" are not easily discoverable when users filter for "<i>interventional studies</i>".</p>
TVS-REL	Relevance	Values accurately align with the intended meaning of the field	<p>Study Metadata Template: Some values do not fully align with the intended meaning of the field. For example, Testing Rate or Uptake does not quite match the meaning of Study Domain.</p>
TVS-CONS	Consistency	Value sets contain appropriate values and consistent	This applies to both the Study Metadata Template and the Data File Metadata Template.

		usage of singular or plural formats	For instance, in the Study Population Focus value sets, values like Immigrants and Asians are consistently presented in plural format.
TVS-LING	Linguistic Quality	Value sets are both grammatically and lexically accurate	This applies to both the Study Metadata Template and the Data File Metadata Template. For instance, some field values make use of acronyms that are not well specified (for example Novel Biosensing or VOC or IRB required)
TVS-STAND	Standardization	Consistent naming conventions, such as camelCase, snake_case, or Title Case, across all value sets, and the use of standardized and uniform values to represent the same concepts or meanings for clarity and coherence	This applies to both the Study Metadata Template and the Data File Metadata Template. For instance, values in the Consent/Data Use Limitations are all in Title Case except for the value IRB required. The correct Title Case format should be IRB Required.

Metadata Evaluation Methods

Automated Evaluation

The **RADx Metadata Evaluator** was developed by the Stanford team specifically to automate metadata evaluations in the RADx Data Hub, aligning its design with criteria tailored to each metadata entity. Currently, the Metadata Evaluator assesses both **data file metadata instances** and **study metadata instances** alongside their respective templates.

The RADx Metadata Evaluator leverages the **Data File Metadata Validator**, a previously developed tool designed to validate JSON-based data file metadata files within the Data Hub. However, since study metadata are evaluated in Excel format rather than JSON, the evaluator integrates the **Spreadsheet Validator**, a separate tool from the Stanford team, to extend its coverage. The evaluator's output takes

the form of comprehensive evaluation reports, which highlight any potential issues and guide subsequent improvements in metadata quality.

Figure 5. Architecture and workflow of the RADx Metadata Evaluator.

Manual Review

In addition to automated methods, manual reviews were conducted to ensure the accuracy, consistency, and completeness of evaluations. This involved verifying issues flagged by the evaluator tool through cross-checking and confirming their validity. Additional manual checks were performed on nuanced or complex fields that were difficult to assess automatically.

For example, large blocks of text, such as those in the Study Description field, are inherently difficult for computer programs to parse or fully comprehend due to their unstructured nature. While automated methods can handle certain general evaluations, they often struggle to capture the nuanced relationships and context within such text, which can lead to errors or oversights. For instance, fields like the Study Population Focus and Data Collection Methods are particularly difficult to extract accurately through automated processes. To address these limitations, manual reviews were conducted to thoroughly examine the study description

content, ensuring that critical details were accurately captured and aligned with the other metadata fields.

Evaluation Reports

The evaluation reports are generated exclusively for internal use and are not published on the RADx Data Hub website. These Excel-format reports are structured into three distinct tabs: **Metadata Evaluation Database**, **Metadata Instances Summary**, and **Templates Summary**. Each tab provides a focused summary of identified issues across the evaluated metadata entities.

	Result ID	PHS	File Location	File Location Comments	Entity Type	Metadata Field	Value	Start Position	End Position	Criterion	
1											
2	21b0efd7-a	phs002516	https://github	Row 7	Study Metadata	acknowledgement_s	This study v	255	298	Accessibility	R/
3	5e931531-	phs002516	https://github	Row 7	Study Metadata	acknowledgement_s	This study v	255	298	Consistency	Di
4	0794ac71-	phs002519	https://github	Row 8	Study Metadata	acknowledgement_s	This study v	255	298	Accessibility	R/
5	a63663aa-	phs002519	https://github	Row 8	Study Metadata	acknowledgement_s	This study v	255	298	Consistency	Di
6	7b5407-	phs002519	https://github.com/basis-edy	Data File	Metadata	Data File	https://01/5/	0	118	Accuracy	Cl

Metadata Evaluation Database | Metadata Instances Summary | Templates Summary

Figure 6. Example of evaluation reports highlighting the Metadata Evaluation Database, Metadata Instances Summary, and Templates Summary tabs.

Metadata Evaluation Database

The Metadata Evaluation Database tab provides a comprehensive list of all identified issues across evaluated metadata entities. Each entry documents critical details about the issue. Below is a detailed explanation of the fields included in the Metadata Evaluation Database:

- **Result ID:** A unique identifier (UUID) assigned to each issue, ensuring traceability and consistency across reports.
- **PHS:** The PHS ID of the study associated with the issue. This links the issue to its respective study for targeted resolution.
- **File Location:** The GitHub URL of the metadata file where the issue was identified.

- **File Location Comments:** Additional details about the file location. For study metadata, this includes the row number where the issue occurs. For data file metadata, this field remains empty.
- **Entity Type:** Specifies the type of entity where the issue was found. Possible values include:
 - *Study Metadata*
 - *Data File Metadata*
 - *Template Fields*
 - *Template Value Sets*
- **Metadata Field:** The name of the specific metadata field that contains the issue.
- **Value:** The original value in the metadata field that was flagged as problematic.
- **Start Position:** The starting index of the issue within the metadata field value.
- **End Position:** The ending index of the issue within the metadata field value.
- **Criterion:** The evaluation criterion that identified the issue. For example, *Completeness, Accuracy, Consistency, or Validity*.
- **Description:** A detailed explanation of the issue, including why it was flagged.
- **Result Level:** Categorizes the issue based on its severity:
 - *Error:* Indicates that the issue requires immediate correction to ensure metadata integrity.
 - *Review Needed:* Suggests that the issue needs further investigation or confirmation.
 - *Info:* Indicates a non-issue, providing informational details. Typically used to display completeness results.
- **Repair Suggestion:** A proposed corrected value or solution for the issue, aiding users in the resolution process.
- **Evaluation Date:** The date when the issue was identified during the metadata evaluation process.
- **Creator:** The name of the entity or tool that identified the issue. If the issue was found by the automated evaluation tool, the value will be *RADx Data Hub Metadata Evaluator*.

- **Fixed Locally:** Indicates whether the issue has been resolved locally, with acceptable values being Yes or No.
- **Applied to Hub:** Specifies whether the resolved issue has been implemented in the Hub, with acceptable values being Yes or No.
- **Comments:** Any additional remarks or contextual information about the issue, which may include suggestions for collaboration or further clarification.

Result ID	PHS	File Location	File Location Comments	Entity Type	Metadata Field	Value	Start Position	End Position	Criterion	Description	Result Level	Repair Suggestion	Evaluation Date	Creator	Fixed Locally	Applied to Hub	Comments	
1223492e-857b-43e8-84b1-ab998f610bd9	phs002917	b.com/bmir-radx/radx-data-hub-metadata/blob/main/%20Study%20	Row 123	Study Metadata	study_website_URL	du/medicine/mherc/news-events/center-news/463-from-mistrust-to-partnership-		0	258	Accessibility	The provided URL contains a text fragment.	Error	Remove text fragments from url	01/29/2025	RADx Data Hub Metadata Evaluator	No	No	

Figure 7. Example of metadata issue in the Metadata Issues Database.

Study Population Focus: Adults; African Americans; Older Adults or Elderly; Racial or Ethnic Minorities; Rural Communities; Underserved or Vulnerable Populations

Study Website URL: [https://www.uab.edu/news/campus/item/12610-respect-up-grant-looks-at-multiple-factors-surrounding-covid-19-testing-in-underserved-communities#:~:text=The%20project,%20titled%20Reducing%20Ethical%20and%20Social%20Prejudicial:](https://www.uab.edu/news/campus/item/12610-respect-up-grant-looks-at-multiple-factors-surrounding-covid-19-testing-in-underserved-communities#:~:text=The%20project,%20titled%20Reducing%20Ethical%20and%20Social%20Prejudicial;)
<https://www.uab.edu/medicine/mherc/news-events/center-news/463-from-mistrust-to-partnership-community-members-lead-the-way-in-overcoming-research-mistrust-in-african-american-communities#:~:text=New%20research%20from%20the%20Reducing%20Ethical%20and%20Social>

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Figure 8. Screenshot of the Study Website URL value for study phs002917 at RADx Data Hub.

Figure 7 illustrates an example of an issue recorded in the Issues Database. In this example, the study with PHS ID phs002917 has an issue located at row 123 of the metadata file, which can be accessed at: https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-data-hub-metadata/blob/main/%20Study%20etadadata/RADx_studies_metadata_01222025.xlsx. The issue is classified as an Accessibility issue in the metadata field study_website_URL.

The issue description specifies that the provided URL contains a text fragment. As shown in Figure 8, two URLs in the Study Website URL field include text fragments,

Data File Metadata												
	Overall Completeness	Required Fields Completeness	Recommended Fields Completeness	Optional Fields Completeness	Consistency	Accuracy	Validity	Accessibility	Controlled Vocabulary Consistency	Uniqueness	Linguistic Quality	Structural Quality
PHS	26.42%	100.00%	85.00%	10.71%	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 10. Data File Metadata Evaluation Summary of a Sample Study.

Figure 10 displays the data file metadata evaluation summary for study phs003374. Completeness scores and identified issues are reported by evaluation criteria:

- **Overall Completeness (26.42%)** : This score represents 26.42% of all metadata fields (required, recommended, and optional) that have been completed with values.
- **Required Fields Completeness (100.00%)**: This score indicates that all required fields have been completed without any missing values.
- **Recommended Fields Completeness (85.00%)**: This score reflects 85% of recommended fields that have been filled.
- **Optional Fields Completeness (10.71%)**: This score represents 10.71% of optional fields that have been completed with values.
- **Consistency (4)**: This number indicates that 4 consistency issues were identified in the data file metadata.

Overall, the results shown in Table 4 represent the average completeness score across all studies. For study metadata instances, the average Overall Completeness is 77.7%, with average Required Fields Completeness at 100% and average Recommended Fields Completeness at 72.91%. In addition, for data file metadata instances, the average Overall Completeness is 26.42%, with average Required Fields Completeness at 100%, average Recommended Fields Completeness at 85%, and average Optional Fields Completeness at 10.71%.

Table 4. Average completeness for study metadata instances and data file metadata instances across all studies.

Criterion ID	Criterion Name	Study Metadata Instances	Data File Metadata Instances
M-COMP	Overall Completeness	77.7%	26.43%
M-COMP-REQ	Completeness of Required Fields	100%	100%
M-COMP-REC	Completeness of Recommended Fields	72.91%	85%
M-COMP-OP	Completeness of Optional Fields	NA	10.71%

Furthermore, Table 5 shows the total number of identified issues across all studies, categorized by evaluation criteria for both study metadata instances and data file metadata instances. In study metadata instances, the highest number of issues was found in Linguistic Quality (123), whereas in data file metadata instances, the highest number of issues was found in Consistency (260). **The issues in the table include both *Error* and *Review Needed* levels.**

Table 5. Total number of identified issues across all studies by criteria

Criterion ID	Criterion Name	Study Metadata Instances	Data File Metadata Instances
M-CONS	Consistency	29	260
M-ACCU	Accuracy	6	0
M-VAL	Validity	0	28
M-ACCE	Accessibility	14	0
M-CVC	Controlled Vocabulary Consistency	115	0
M_UNIQ	Uniqueness	0	0

M-LIN	Linguistic Quality	123	20
M-STRUCT	Structural Quality	1	0
	Total	288	308

Templates Summary

The Templates Summary tab provides a summary of the evaluation results for metadata templates, including the total number of identified issues categorized by evaluation criteria (e.g., Completeness, Accuracy, Relevance, Accessibility) and the distribution of issues by template. **The issues include both *Error* and *Review Needed* levels.**

(a)

	Template Fields							
Template	Completeness	Accuracy	Relevance	Accessibility	Structural Quality	Linguistic Quality	Documentation	Standardization
Study Metadata Template	0	2	0	0	0	3	0	0
Data File Metadata Template	1	7	8	1	7	12	0	0

(b)

	Template Value Sets						
Template	Completeness	Accuracy	Relevance	Accessibility	Linguistic Quality	Consistency	Standardization
Study Metadata Template	0	1	1	0	1	0	2
Data File Metadata Template	2	0	0	0	0	0	0

(c)

	Totals		
Template	Total Fields Issues	Total Value Sets Issues	Total Issues
Study Metadata Template	5	5	10
Data File Metadata Template	36	2	38

Figure 11. *Templates Metadata Evaluation Summary. (a) Issue counts for template fields across different criteria. (b) Issue counts for template value sets across different criteria. (c) Total issue counts for fields and value sets combined.*

As shown in Figure 11, a total of 10 issues were identified in the study metadata template: 5 issues in the template fields and 5 in the template value sets. Similarly, 38 issues were identified in the data file metadata template: 36 in the fields and 2 in the value sets.

Evaluation Results

As of January 30, 2025, we evaluated 181 study metadata instances provided by the Booz Allen Hamilton (BAH) team on January 22, 2025; 218 data file metadata instances supplied by BAH on December 12, 2024; one study metadata template; and one data file metadata template.

In total, 586 issues were identified, with an additional 58 requiring further confirmation. The evaluation date for each issue is recorded in the “Evaluation Date” column of the **Metadata Evaluation Database** tab in the evaluation reports. All 586 confirmed issues were identified from metadata instances. To provide a clearer understanding of the findings, a detailed statistical analysis was conducted, focusing on both Study Metadata and Data File Metadata. This analysis highlights the distribution of errors and issues across various criteria, offering insights into key areas that require attention and improvement. **The issues in the visuals below include only Error level.**

Figure 12 presents the analysis results for study metadata issues. Issues requiring further confirmation are excluded from this analysis. A total of 278 issues were identified across various criteria relating to 134 distinct studies. The majority of these issues (123) pertain to the Linguistic Quality criterion, with grammatical errors in the study descriptions accounting for 118 of them. The second most prevalent category is Controlled Vocabulary Consistency with 115 issues, where metadata fields contain values that fall outside the predefined allowed sets. Additionally, 26 issues were identified under the Consistency criterion, indicating discrepancies across different metadata fields. Furthermore, 14 records were flagged under the Accessibility criterion due to broken links found in various metadata fields.

Figure 13 presents the analysis results for data file metadata issues. As with previous analyses, issues requiring further confirmation are not included. A total of 308 issues were identified relating to 172 distinct data file metadata files and to 79 distinct studies. The majority of these issues were, with the majority falling under the Consistency criterion. The most common issue, observed in 134 records, involves inconsistencies between the Study Name field and the corresponding

name in the study metadata. Additionally, there are a combined 124 records where either the Family Name or the Given Name of the data file creator is not consistent with the provided full name.

Study Metadata

Issues per Metadata Field

Issues per Metadata Evaluation Criterion

Issue Count Distinct Studies
278 **134**

Metadata Issue Types

Issue Description Type	Criterion	Record Count
Grammar error	Linguistic Quality	118
The value does not match any allowed value in the set.	Controlled Vocabulary Consistency	115
RAPIDS link in 'acknowledgement_statement' returns non-200 status code (404)	Accessibility	10
Different links found in Acknowledgement Statement and RAPIDS Link field	Consistency	9
'grant_number' doesn't match the grant number in 'acknowledgement_group'	Consistency	5
Extra space(s) found	Linguistic Quality	5
Estimated participants mentioned in 'description' doesn't match the value in 'estimated_participants'	Consistency	4
Estimated participants does not match estimated participant range	Consistency	3
The provided URL contains a text fragment.	Accessibility	3
PI name does not follow last name, first name format	Consistency	2
The link in RAPIDS_link returns non-200 status code (404)	Accessibility	1
'institutes_supporting_study' does not match 'acknowledgement_statement'	Consistency	1
Inconsistency in empty values: some values in 'foa_number' column have "N/A" while others are "NULL"	Consistency	1
'has_data_files' field doesn't match actual number of files present	Consistency	1

1 - 14 / 14 < >

Figure 12. Summary of metadata issues in study metadata.

Data File Metadata

Issues per Metadata Field

Issues per Metadata Evaluation Criterion

Issue Count	Distinct Data File Metadata Files	Distinct Studies
308	172	79

Metadata Issue Types

Issue Description Type	Criterion	Record Count
Study Name does not match the study metadata	Consistency	134
Creator Family Name is inconsistent with the provided full name	Consistency	64
Creator Given Name is inconsistent with the provided full name	Consistency	60
Extra space(s) found	Linguistic Quality	20
An empty string was detected in the Attribute Value field, which is not permitted.	Validity	14
Object instance has properties which are not allowed by the schema	Validity	14
PHS Identifier does not match the study metadata	Consistency	2

1 - 7 / 7 < >

Figure 13. Summary of metadata issues in data file metadata.

Both study metadata and data file metadata exhibit issues related to Consistency and Linguistic Quality criteria. Inconsistencies occur frequently in both study and data file metadata but manifest differently. In study metadata, inconsistencies arise within various fields, such as “Estimated participants does not match estimated participant range.” In data file metadata, inconsistencies not only occur within different fields - such as “Creator Family Name is inconsistent with the provided full name” - but also between study-level and data file-level metadata, exemplified by “Study Name in the data file metadata does not match the study metadata.” Linguistic quality issues, such as “Extra space(s) found”, are present in both study and data file metadata. However, since study metadata contains more text-rich fields (e.g., description), grammar errors are more prevalent. Validity issues are

unique to data file metadata. Additionally, Accessibility issues, such as broken RAPIDS links, appear only in study metadata.

Ongoing Evaluation

This report highlights the methods designed and implemented by the Stanford team to identify and report issues within the RADx Data Hub, along with the results of applying these methods to its current content. This process has led to the identification of an initial list of issues that will be addressed in the coming months through a collaborative effort with the BAH team. Certain tasks, such as verifying the consistency and accuracy of study descriptions against other metadata fields, require significant manual effort and are ongoing. This iterative evaluation and improvement process demonstrates our commitment to continuously enhancing metadata quality, ensuring the RADx Data Hub remains a reliable and user-friendly resource.

Resources

- Evaluation Report
https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-data-hub-metadata/blob/main/Evaluation%20Reports/RADxMetadataEvaluationResults_01302025.xlsx
- RADx Metadata Evaluator:
<https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-metadata-evaluator>
- Radx Data Hub metadata instances:
<https://github.com/bmir-radx/radx-data-hub-metadata>
- Data File Metadata Template
<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2Fc691629c-1183-4425-9a12-26201eab1a10>
- Study Metadata Template
<https://openview.metadatascenter.org/templates/https:%2F%2Frepo.metadatascenter.org%2Ftemplates%2Fe3f0d7c8-777d-4b4d-8c3e-5fbee0bdeec1>

Glossary

- **Data File:** An individual file contains data generated from research studies. RADx studies typically have multiple data files, consisting of phenotypic data collected on study participants, such as demographics, survey, laboratory results, etc.
- **Data File Metadata:** Information describing the data contained in a study, including fields such as Title, File Name, Version, Study Name, PHS Identifier, and other relevant fields.
- **Data File Metadata File:** A file that contains data file metadata.
- **Data File Metadata Instance:** One data file metadata file contains one data file metadata instance.
- **Metadata:** Supplemental information that enhances the interpretability and reusability of scientific data.
- **Metadata Instance:** A specific, concrete metadata record that is created based on a predefined template.
- **Study Metadata:** Additional information at the study level, encompassing fields such as study design, study description, study domain, data collection methods, and other relevant fields.
- **Study Metadata Instance:** A concrete metadata record of study metadata.
- **Template:** A predefined structure or model that serves as a blueprint for organizing and capturing data consistently.
- **Template Field:** A standardized data element or placeholder within a template that defines the structure and organization of information.
- **Template Value Set:** A predefined list or collection of permissible values for specific template fields.